

Kruskal-Wallis One Way Analysis of Variance on Ranks

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Data source: Plasma insulin 15 weeks Notebook2.JNB

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk): Passed (P = 0,399)

Equal Variance Test (Brown-Forsythe): Passed (P = 0,713)

Group	N	Missing	Median	25%	75%
Control	10	0	2,446	0,446	4,121
HI	41	0	5,111	2,794	6,004
HG	12	0	1,095	0,616	2,270

H = 22,510 with 2 degrees of freedom. (P = <0,001)

The differences in the median values among the treatment groups are greater than would be expected by chance; there is a statistically significant difference (P = <0,001)

To isolate the group or groups that differ from the others use a multiple comparison procedure.

All Pairwise Multiple Comparison Procedures (Dunn's Method) :

Comparison	Diff of Ranks	Q	P	P<0,050
HI vs HG	24,726	4,110	<0,001	Yes
HI vs Control	20,576	3,183	0,004	Yes
Control vs HG	4,150	0,529	1,000	No

Note: The multiple comparisons on ranks do not include an adjustment for ties.